

PARACHOR OF IONS

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Parachors of NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl, NaNO₃, K₂CO₃ and KBr at various concentrations have been determined and it is shown that the values obtained are much smaller than those calculated by summing up the parachors of the constituent atoms. It is further shown that Mumford and Phillip's values for ions do not reproduce experimental results for electrolytes in solution.

The atomic parachors of alkali metal as calculated by Sugden from Jaeger's results have been shown to be incorrect.

Mumford's method of calculating ionic parachor from the parachor of fused salts is not correct as at the temperatures mentioned the salts may not have been wholly in the ionic state. Further, according to Born there should be a fixed ratio between the parachors of ions and atoms of the same group and the value should be less than unity. The values as calculated from fused salts do not give this ratio a constant value for alkali metals, although the ratio is less than 1 as is expected.

The method of calculating atomic parachors from the solutions of electrolytes is shown to be incorrect, since electrolytes exist in solution as ions and not as atoms. An expression,

$$P_1 + P_2 = P_m = \frac{\{(1-\alpha) P_p + (1-\alpha)x P_x\}}{\alpha x}$$

has been derived for calculating the sum of the ionic parachors and has been applied to K₂CO₃, KI, NH₄NO₃, KCl, NaCl and NH₄Cl with fairly constant results. Further, it is shown that $P_1 + P_2$ (ionic) is different from the sum of the atomic parachors. Thus it is shown that ions have fixed parachors which are different from those of atoms. This view is supported further from Ray's results.

Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 43) and Lakhani and Daroga (*ibid.*, 1938, 15, 37, 519, 604) have determined the parachors of some electrolytes in aqueous solutions. Lakhani and Daroga (*loc cit.*) had no clear conception of that the values obtained were for ions and not for atoms. Hence they made an attempt to evaluate atomic parachors from the values obtained for electrolytes. Further, they found that the formula

$$P_m = (1-x)F + xP_x$$

was not applicable, and hence tried to suggest a modification. All this confusion was due to the fact that they did not realise that the values obtained were for compounds in the ionised state.

Ray (*loc cit.*) and Bhagwat and Toshniwal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 192; 1944, 21, 53, 61) have shown that the parachor of an electrolyte is different from that of the sum of the constituent atoms. In other words, atomic and ionic parachors are not identical. Further, the value varies with dilution. We have extended this work and our results for some salts are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Substance.	α .	P_x at			
		25°.	30°.	40°.	50°.
I. K_2CO_3 ,	0.0609	143.8	143.4	140.6	140.6
	0.0723	148.7	147.3	146.9	145.5
	0.0869	156.8	154.5	153.3	153.3
	0.0985	159.0	158.2	158.0	158.0
	0.1125	163.4	162.4	162.0	162.3
	0.1209	169.3	168.8	168.1	167.8
II. KOI	0.0261	101.2	98.7	101.2	98.7
	0.0405	102.5	102.2	100.4	100.7
	0.0570	108.1	108.1	101.2	101.4
III. NaCl	0.0329	70.8	67.5	67.9	68.1
	0.0514	74.5	74.5	73.7	72.7
	0.0712	76.8	76.3	75.6	76.1
	0.0930	77.5	76.4	76.5	75.8
IV. NH_4Cl	0.0365	...	123.5	120.5	121.1
	0.0537	...	125.3	125.9	122.2
	0.1020	...	128.1	128.6	127.8
V. $NaNO_3$	0.0230	77.82	85.65	85.48	83.0
	0.0506	94.2	96.6	95.6	95
	0.0686	105.5	106.3	106.2	107.5
VI. KBr	0.0164	114.6	117.6	116.4	...
	0.0364	118.9	114.5	120.3	123.1
	0.0609	116.4	121.0	122.6	120.3

Unfortunately the values for atomic parachor of sodium and potassium from covalent compounds are unknown. If, however, we consider the values $Na=80$ and $K=110$, as given by Sugden, the values for K_2CO_3 , $NaCl$, NH_4Cl , KCl , KI , NH_4NO_3 , KBr and $NaNO_3$ will be 283.2, 134.3, 135.2, 164.3, 201, 175, 178 and 174.1 respectively. The observed values are much lower than these. In case of ammonium nitrate and chloride, the values for the constituent atoms are known from covalent compounds, and hence there is no doubt that the ionic and atomic parachors are different.

DISCUSSION

Sugden and Wilkins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1291) have used surface tensions of fused salts determined by Jaeger (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 1) at various temperatures to determine the atomic parachors of alkali metals. In the opinion of the present authors, the work at these high temperatures is not trustworthy. A single case of salts of lithium will illustrate this.

TABLE II

Salt.	Temp.	Parachor.	Mean <i>P.</i>	$\Sigma P.$	Atomic P_{Li}
LiF	850°—1000°	57.8—59.3	58.5	24.1	34.4
LiCl	600°—775°	97.2—99.6	98.4	52.7	45.7
LiNO ₃	850°—500°	130—132.9	131.5	91.5	40.0
Li ₂ SO ₄	860°—1160°	212—220	216.0	121.8	2 × 47.1

The mean of these values is not 50 which is taken as the atomic parachor of Li. The selection by Sugden is purely arbitrary not only in this case but same is true for his values of atomic parachors of Na, K, Rb and Cs. Mumford and Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2130) object to the use of one and the same atomic constant for the combined atom and for the ion of an element, by Sugden and Wilkins (*loc. cit.*). They believe that at these high temperatures and in fused state the salt ionises and the ions and not the atoms are existing.

If in accordance with the views of Born (*Z. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45) the volume measured by the parachor is regarded as being directly and simply related to the actual dimensions of the molecule or atom concerned (cf. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1055), then the parachor values of the ions of the halogens may be approximately estimated from the atomic parachors of rare gases which follow them in periodic classification. Calculation on this basis (Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 465) indicates that the parachor values of halide ions should on an average be 1.46 times those of the atoms of the corresponding rare gases, and hence about 1.44 times those of the halogen atoms in non-polar combination. The approximate ionic parachors obtained by this method are F' = 36, Cl' = 79, Br' = 99, I' = 130. When these values are subtracted from the observed parachors of the fused alkali metal salts, the ionic parachors of these alkali metals are obtained. Thus, we have Li = 21, Na = 45, K = 76, Rb = 95 and Cs = 109. On similar lines the parachor values for NO₃' , PO₃' and SO₄' ions are obtained. Thus, NO₃' = 109, PO₃' = 132 and SO₄' = 172. This procedure of calculating ionic parachor from the observed values of the parachors of fused salts is in the opinion of the authors highly objectionable, since the parachor values at these high temperatures are not accurate. A rough idea of this variation will be obtained from the following table.

TABLE III

Salt.	Parachor.	Salt.	Parachor.
Li ₂ SO ₄	212.4—220.6	NaNO ₃	147.9—158.4
Na ₂ SO ₄	257.5—265.8	KNO ₃	184.2—193.6
K ₂ SO ₄	319.5—326.5	RbNO ₃	192.5—203.7
Rb ₂ SO ₄	356.9—368.1	Cs ₂ SO ₄	386.8—398.1

Secondly, it is assumed that in fused state at the temperature range examined, the salts ionise completely. No evidence has been produced to show

that ionisation is not partial but complete in all cases. Thirdly, just as the ionic parachors of halide ions are on average x times (1.44) the parachor of corresponding atom, so the parachor value of ions of alkali metal should also be m [m should be less than unity since according to Born (*loc. cit.*) positive ions have smaller volume than the corresponding atoms) times the atomic parachor of the corresponding atom. - The ratio of ionic parachor as calculated above and of atomic parachor by Sugden is as follows

TABLE IV

Element.	P_{ion} .	P_{atom} .	Ratio, $m = \frac{P_{\text{ion}}}{P_{\text{atom}}}$.	Group.	P_{ion} .	P_{atom} .	m .
Na	46	80	0.58	NO ₃ '	109	94.1	1.16
K	76	110	0.69	PO ₃ '	182	119.8	1.10
Li	21	50	0.42	SO ₄ "	172	125	1.33
Rb	95	180	0.73				
Cs	109	150	0.73				

The results with alkali metals show that the value of m varies appreciably. The ions NO₃' and PO₃' are similar in structure and the values of m in two cases agree appreciably. Fortunately here, the values of atomic parachor of N, O, P and S are known directly from covalent compounds. The values for parachors of NaCl, NaNO₃, KI, KBr and KCl, as calculated from the results of Mumford and Phillip, are 124, 154, 206, 175 and 153 respectively. The observed values in solution are much smaller than these. Thus Mumford and Phillip's values fail to reproduce experimental results.

It will be clear from the above discussion that no reliable values of ionic parachor even for thermal ionisation are known.

Lakhani and Daroga (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 37) were the first to study the parachor of inorganic salts, but it seems that they were not aware of the work of Mumford and Phillip (*loc. cit.*) on the parachor of ions in fused state. They therefore wrongly tried to determine the atomic parachors of metallic elements from the parachor of salts which ionise in aqueous solutions (*ibid.*, 1938, 15, 604, 37, 519).

Toshniwal (thesis submitted to Agra University, 1945) has tried to show that ions have specific parachor values by considering the salts at equimolecular concentrations, assuming that they ionise equally at these concentrations. He did not attempt to calculate the actual values of individual ions, but applied Kohlrausch principle of mobilities of ions that as strong electrolytes ionise completely $P_{\text{NaCl}} - P_{\text{KCl}} = P_{\text{NaNO}_3} - P_{\text{KNO}_3}$. He showed that approximately constant results were obtained. The work therefore is incomplete. In this paper we have attempted to show that ions have definite parachor values by showing that sum of ionic parachor at different dilutions is constant, taking into consideration the degrees of ionisation as obtained from the corresponding

values of μ_v/μ^∞ and applying the viscosity correction. These results are available from the Standard Tables.

Hence, values for such salts alone are calculated from the results given by us in previous pages, for which μ_v/μ^∞ and viscosity data are available.

The following expression is derived by us for determining the ionic parachor.

Let the molecular fraction of the electrolyte (binary) and of the solvent in a solution be x and $1-x$ respectively. Let α be the degree of ionisation of the salt in this solution. Let M_p be the molecular weight of the solvent, M_x , the molecular weight of the salt and M_1 and M_2 be the weights of cation and anion, such that $M_x = M_1 + M_2$. The number of ions of each kind present in the solution is thus αx and the number of molecules of solute left is $(1-\alpha)x$. The total number of individuals in solution is now

$$= 1-x \text{ (of solvent)} + (1-\alpha)x \text{ of the salt} + \alpha x \text{ of cations} + \alpha x \text{ of anions} \\ = 1 + \alpha x.$$

$$\text{Hence the molar fraction of the solvent} = \frac{1-x}{1+\alpha x}$$

$$\text{" " undissociated molecules of salt} = \frac{(1-\alpha)x}{1+\alpha x}$$

$$\text{" " each ion} = \frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x} \text{ cation}$$

$$\frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x} \text{ anion}$$

Thus the mean molecular weight

$$M_3 = \frac{(1-x)M_p}{1+\alpha x} + \frac{(1-\alpha)xM_x}{1+\alpha x} + \frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x}M_1 + \frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x}M_2$$

$$\text{or } (1+\alpha x)M_3 = (1-x)M_p + (1-\alpha)xM_x + \alpha xM_1 + \alpha xM_2 \\ = (1-x)M_p + (1-\alpha)xM_x + \alpha x(M_1 + M_2)$$

$$\text{But } M_1 + M_2 = M_x$$

$$\text{Hence } (1+\alpha x)M_3 = (1-x)M_p + xM_x.$$

But by Hammick and Andrew's equation

$$M_m = (1-x)M_p + xM_x$$

$$\text{Hence } (1+\alpha x)M_3 = M_m.$$

The parachor of the solution is given by :

$$P_3 = \frac{M_3 r^{\frac{1}{2}}}{d} = \frac{M_m}{(1+\alpha x)d} r^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{But } P_m = \frac{M_m r^{\frac{1}{2}}}{d} \text{ or } P_3(1+\alpha x) = P_m.$$

$$\text{Also, } P_3 = \frac{1-x}{1+\alpha x} P_p + \frac{(1-\alpha)x}{1+\alpha x} P_x + \frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x} P_1 + \frac{\alpha x}{1+\alpha x} P_2$$

$$\text{or } (1+\alpha x)P_3 = (1-x)P_p + (1-\alpha)xP_x + \alpha x(P_1 + P_2)$$

$$\text{or } P_m = (1-x)P_p + (1-\alpha)xP_x + \alpha x(P_1 + P_2)$$

$$\text{or } P_1 + P_2 = \frac{P_m - \{(1-x)P_p + (1-\alpha)xP_x\}}{\alpha x}$$

For P_s , the parachor of undissociated molecules of the salt, the values given by Sugden are used. The results will show that the sum of ionic parachors is less than that for undissociated molecules, indicating that ions and molecules have different parachor constants. Further, although varying concentrations are used, the result for sum of ionic parachors is practically constant, showing that ions have fixed parachor constants. The results have also been calculated from Ray's observations (*loc. cit.*). In all cases the constancy is fair considering the fact that molar fractions in all cases are low, as the amount that can be dissolved at a fixed temperature is fixed by the solubility of the salt. The results of Ray are not identical with those of ours; they are, however, among themselves constant. The variation is due to the fact that a slight variation in P_m has an immense effect on the final calculation, since molar fractions of the salt are low. The molar fraction varies from $M/100$ to $M/10$ and therefore the error present in P_m may be magnified from 10 to 100 times in calculating $P_1 + P_2$.

TABLE V

NH ₄ Cl.						
α .	$\mu\theta$.	$\mu\infty$.	$\mu\theta/\mu\infty$.	$\eta\theta/\eta\infty$.	α .	NH ₄ ⁺ +Cl ⁻ .
0.0865	92.4		0.7638	0.9730	0.7429	125.7
0.0567	88.4	121.0	0.7805	0.9708	0.7088	123.1
0.1020	80.5		0.6609	0.9642	0.6429	123.0

The value for (NH₄⁺+Cl⁻) from Ray's results (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15 44) varies from 105—112 when α varies from 0.017 to 0.099.

KI.						
α .	$\mu\theta$.	$\mu\infty$.	$\mu\theta/\mu\infty$.	$\eta\theta/\eta\infty$.	α .	K ⁺ +Cl ⁻ .
0.0325	102.2		0.7861	0.921	0.7130	129.7
0.0491	98.8	130.27	0.7600	0.9178	0.6869	130.8
0.0789	90.0		0.6928	0.9150	0.6238	127.2
0.0989	88.7		0.6438	0.9124	0.5794	125.5

Values calculated from Ray's results for (K⁺+Cl⁻) vary from 100 to 109 when α varies from 0.041 to 0.096.

K ₂ CO ₃ .						2K ⁺ +CO ₃ ²⁻
α .	$\mu\theta$.	$\mu\infty$.	$\mu\theta/\mu\infty$.	$\eta\theta/\eta\infty$.	α .	
0.0609	35.1		0.2315	2.3815	0.6704	74.2
0.0723	29.86	124.8	0.2315	2.7707	0.6414	69.8
0.1209	13.0		0.1043	5.4808	0.5616	79.1
0.1125	14.08		0.1127	4.6992	0.5296	59.0
0.0935	20.74		0.1663	3.8293	0.6368	86.8
	23.54		0.1838	3.3853	0.6391	83.1

TABLE V

ω .	μv .	$\mu \infty$.	KCl		α .	K ⁺ +Cl ⁻ .
			$\mu v/\mu \infty$.	$\eta v/\eta \infty$.		
0.0261	95.2		0.7328	0.9887	0.7225	76.9
0.0406	91.5	130.11	0.7088	0.9969	0.7088	76.0
0.06708	88.9		0.6828	1.011	0.6918	75.8
0.01822	93.22		0.7554	0.982	0.7420	75.2

Values calculated from Rays' results vary from 81 to 85 when ω varies from 0.01 to 0.04.

NH₄NO₃.

	μv .	$\mu \infty$.	NH ₄ ⁺ +NO ₃ ⁻			
			$\mu v/\mu \infty$.	$\eta v/\eta \infty$.	α .	
0.0243	85.9		0.7820	1.1480	0.8408	148.6
0.0525	76.0	117.34	0.6477	1.1819	0.7331	154.0
0.0880	67.1		0.5718	1.1725	0.6708	146.4

Values calculated from Ray's results vary from 140 to 155 as ω varies from 0.04 to 0.18.

NaCl.

$P_{\text{used}} = 124.8$

	μv .	$\mu \infty$.	Na ⁺ +Cl ⁻			
			$\mu v/\mu \infty$.	$\eta v/\eta \infty$.	α .	
0.3289	66.2		0.6078	1.1559	0.702	48.8
0.0514	57.8		0.5303	1.2426	0.659	40.9
0.7127	49.9	108.99	0.4578	1.3411	0.614	40.7
0.0180	74.81		0.6817	1.0868	0.741	40.9

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